

Relationship Between Occupation and Empowerment of Women

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ABSTRACT

Women's empowerment has become a significant topic of discussion in development policies and economics. Economic empowerment allows women to control and benefit from resources, assets, and income. It also aids in the ability to manage risks and improve women's well-being. It is widely believed that female employment and empowerment are intimately related. This paper presents relationships between women's employment and various measures of their empowerment, using data from Nagaon district of Assam. The measures capture several dimensions of empowerment, including control in household decision-making, freedom of movement and political participation. A number of these measures correlate positively with women's employment, supporting the notion that female employment and empowerment are closely linked.

KEYWORDS: Empowerment, Women, livelihood pattern

INTRODUCTION

Empowerment is a global issue. The development policies and schemes of every developing country are concerned with the issue of women empowerment. Women empowerment is regarded as a part of sustainable development.

The concept of empowerment has occupied a central place in the work of many development policies of the nations. Empowerment can be viewed as the process of enabling individual to think, to take action and control work in an autonomous way. It is the process by which one can gain control over his or her own resources and the circumstances of their lives. Therefore, empowerment is one of the ways of creating a social environment in which one can make decision of their own life and can make choices individually. Empowerment refers to increasing spiritual, economic, political, social, educational and gender strength of individuals and communities. The concept of empowerment is multidimensional. Empowerment can be viewed as economic empowerment, social empowerment, political empowerment, educational empowerment, community empowerment etc.

The present study makes an attempt to analyze the level of women empowerment. The geographical area

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selected for the study is Nagaon district of Assam and to examine the linkage between the occupation and status of the women empowerment of the district.

Objectives

The objectives of the study are:

1. To study the level of women empowerment in Nagaon district by constructing and estimating women empowerment index.
2. To examine the linkage between women empowerment and her occupational status in Nagaon district of Assam.

Methodology and the Design of the study

The study is based on primary data and the target group population comprises of adult women belonging to the age group of 18-60 years. The reason for identification of this group is in the line of the study that focuses on empowerment and workforce participation of women. For the study a sample of 200 households are selected at random from Nagaon district. A structured interview schedule is prepared for collecting primary data through household survey. Direct interview method is used for collection of data and the data are collected from both employed and unemployed women.

The basic segments which constitute the level of women empowerment are her ability to take decision within family, her freedom of movement and her political participation. The variables which are used in this study to measure women empowerment in its above mentioned three constituent parts are defined below.

Decision making within family: The decision-making ability of women within the family is judged by her decision-making power in regard to Family Health Care, Larger household purchases, Routine household purchases, Family size, Family planning, Job of woman, Going outside home, Family day to day expenditure and Spending personal income. In regard to each of these variables, value assigned is 1 if woman is found to be able to take decision independently; 0.5 if she takes decision after discussion with other family member(s) and; 0 if she has no role to play in decision making.

Freedom of movement: The variables representing freedom of movement are women’s ability to move freely for Local market for purchase, Local health centre/clinic, Gossiping in the neighborhood, Visiting home of relatives/friends, Visiting other city or village , Recreation in cinema hall, club, festival or village fair etc., visiting parental home, Participating in cultural program of village/town , Participating in religious program of village /town , Participating in the meeting of women organizations, Doing job/work outside home for self-earnings.

As like previous case, each of the said variables are quantified as 1 if woman has full freedom of movement; 0.5 if woman moves out after having discussion with other member(s) of the family and; 0 if woman has no freedom of movement.

Political participation- The following variables define the constituent part of Political Participation of women empowerment. Ability to - cast vote in election, Vote to a candidate of choice, Attend the speeches of the election candidates, Update self about the political system and, Talk to political leaders/representatives in need. The values assigned to each of these variables are as follows – 1 if woman enjoy full freedom of political participation; 0.5 if she has partial freedom; and 0 if the woman has no freedom of participation.

Fuzzy set technique is used to analyze and interpret the data in the present study. The mathematical framework of the same is presented below.

Let X be a set and x some elements of X and E is the fuzzy subset which represents the set of empowered women. The degree of membership to the fuzzy set E

of the *i*-th individual (*i* = 1, ..., *n*) with respect to the *j*-th attribute (*j* = 1, ... , *m*) is defined as

$$\mu_E \left(X_j \left(a_i \right) \right) = x_{ij} \quad 0 \leq x_{ij} \leq 1$$

Where

1. $x_{ij} = 1$ if the *i*-th individual is fully empowered with respect to the *j*-th attribute;
2. $x_{ij} = 0$ if the *i*-th individual is not empowered with respect to the *j*-th attribute
3. $0 \leq x_{ij} \leq 1$ if the *i*-th individual is partially empowered with respect to the *j*-th attribute with an intensity belonging to the open interval (0,1).

The empowerment index of the *i*-th individual $\mu_E(a_i)$ i.e. the degree of membership of *i*-th individual to the fuzzy set E is defined as the weighted average of x_{ij} ,

$$\mu_E \left(a_i \right) = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^m x_{ij} w_j}{\sum_{j=1}^m w_j}$$

Where w_j the weight attached to the *j*-th attribute.

The empowerment index $\mu_E(a_i)$ measures the degree of empowerment of the *i*-th individual as a weighting function of the *m* attributes. Hence, it measures the intensity to empowerment of the *i*-th individual subject to decision making, freedom of movement and political participation.

In this way it is possible to get the multidimensional empowerment index of the population.

Data Analysis and Discussion

From the study following results and findings can be drawn in case of Nagaon district-

Table 1 Degree of Empowerment and Weighted Women Empowerment Index

Attributes	$\mu_E \left(X_j \right)$	W_j	$\mu_E \left(X_j \right) W_j$
X_1 (Decision making within the family)	0.6102	0.2145	0.1308
X_2 (Freedom of movement)	0.4778	0.3207	0.1532
X_3 (Political Participation)	0.608	0.2161	0.1313

Source- estimated by the researcher

In Table-1, X_1 represents respondent’s decision making power within the family. X_2 represents respondent’s freedom of movement and X_3 represents

respondent's political participation. $\mu_E(X_j)$ represents degree to empowerment according to the attributes, w_j indicates the weight of the attributes and $\mu_E(X_j)w_j$ represents weighted women empowerment index.

Now the overall women empowerment index (WEI) is calculated by using the formula

$$WEI = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^m \mu_E(X_j)w_j}{\sum_{j=1}^m w_j} \text{----- (i)}$$

$$= 0.4153 / 0.7513$$

$$= 0.5527$$

From the above formula (i) it is seen that the overall women empowerment index of Nagaon district is only 0.55 in the range of (0,1).

Sub group empowerment decomposition

It is possible to decompose women empowerment index by sub population. Suppose the total population is divided into K groups - S_k , of size n_k ($k=1,2,\dots,K$).

The intensity of women empowerment of i -th individual of S_k is given by

$$\mu_E(a_i^k) = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^m x_{ij}^k w_j}{\sum_{j=1}^m w_j}$$

Where x_{ij}^k is the degree of membership related to the fuzzy sub set E of i -th individual ($i=1,2,\dots,n$) of S_k with respect to the j -th attribute ($j=1,2,\dots,m$). Hence, the fuzzy women empowerment associated with group S_k is:

$$\mu_E^k = 1/n_k \sum_{i=1}^{n_k} \mu_E(a_i^k)$$

Here total 200 respondents are divided into four groups of occupation on the basis of their level of income. The groups are as follows-

1. Group A (Income more than Rs.40000 per month)
2. Group B (Income between Rs.20000 to Rs.40000 per month)
3. Group C (income between Rs.1000 to Rs.20000 per month)
4. Group D (The unemployed and those whose income is less than Rs.1000 per month)

After analyzing the data according to the groups, the result obtained are shown in Table-2.

Table-2 Occupation category and Empowerment

Group	WEI
Group A	0.61
Group B	0.58
Group C	0.55
Group D	0.46

Source-estimated by the researcher

From the above table it is seen that the average women empowerment index of the district is only 0.5527. The reason for this low level of empowerment appears to be limited livelihood options for the women of the district. Besides this, because of low literacy level women section of rural areas is less aware about the various development policies and program of the government. From the table it can be said that the women of group A whose income is more than Rs.40000 have higher empowerment value than the others and the women of group D who are unemployed or having income less than Rs. 1000 have lowest empowerment value. The income- based occupational position is found to have strong linkage with women empowerment because those women who are working as Group A workers have more decision-making power within family, freedom of movement and also active in political participation than those women who are unemployed. Thus, we can say that there is positive correlation between occupational status of women and their empowerment.

Conclusion

The results show that the contributions of the three selected constituents i.e. women's decision-making power within the family, freedom of movement and political participation to this women empowerment level is a pointer towards the complex social system of the study area which is more or less similar in other parts of the backward societies of India. Women belonging to higher income groups have higher empowerment level than lower income and unemployed groups. This is probably because of higher prerogatives and position associated with higher occupations that enable a woman to raise her voice in household decision making process, to move around with more freedom and also to participate more actively in political system. Similarly, the urban women are more empowered than the rural women. The implication of this result points towards the importance of higher and quality education for women, diversification of livelihood options for them and implementation of governmental affirmative program for the social development of women.

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